

Towards Enabling Scalable Federation Solutions: Findings from the PANORAMA Early Adopter Project

Katherine O’Sullivan, Katherine Bishop, Phil Waywell,
Alan Bagnall, Helen Duckworth

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PANORAMA Final Project Report

Authors

Katherine O'Sullivan (Research Data Scotland [current]; University of Sheffield [previous]; Yorkshire & Humber Secure Data Environment [previous]) – ORCID: 0000-0002-9225-4942

Katherine Bishop (University of Sheffield; Yorkshire & Humber Secure Data Environment) – ORCID: 0009-0001-8723-5114

Phil Waywell (Health Innovation Yorkshire & Humber; Yorkshire & Humber Secure Data Environment) – ORCID: 0009-0005-0036-0019

Alan Bagnall (Newcastle Hospitals NHS Foundation Trust; North East & North Cumbria Secure Data Environment) – ORCID: 0000-0003-0683-851X

Helen Duckworth (NHS Arden & GEM Commissioning Support Unit; North West Secure Data Environment)

1. Project Overview

1.1. Executive Project Summary

The Pan-North Data Research Advancements for Multi-Domain Access and Analysis (PANORAMA) project aimed to explore how sensitive data can be shared and analysed securely across multiple organisations without requiring row-level data to be moved or pooled into a single location, an approach commonly referred to as 'federation' [1]. This challenge is increasingly important as researchers seek to address complex questions that span healthcare, population health, and other public sector domains, while continuing to meet public expectations around data privacy, security, and appropriate use.

Trusted Research Environments (TREs) are secure computing environments that allow approved researchers to access sensitive data under strict technical and governance controls. While TREs are now well established across the UK, they have historically been developed independently, resulting in differences in technical design, governance processes, and operational practice. In addition, federated access across TREs is typically implemented on a project-by-project basis, requiring bespoke governance

arrangements for each individual study. This per-project approach is time-consuming, treats research projects in isolation, and limits opportunities to develop scalable solutions that would enable faster, more consistent researcher access to data. Together, these factors make collaboration across TREs difficult and constrain the potential for large-scale, multi-site research.

As a DARE UK [TREvolution Early Adopter](#) project, PANORAMA aimed to address these challenges by assessing the feasibility of using a set of emerging tools to enable a secure, connected and interoperable network of TREs. Specifically, the project worked with [Standard Architecture for Trusted Research Environments](#) (SATRE), the [5 Safes Trusted Execution Service](#) (5STES), and [Semi-Automated Checking of Research Outputs](#) (SACRO) to assess the usability of these tools to establish a Pan-North NHS Secure Data Environment federation. Led by researchers at the University of Sheffield, PANORAMA is a collaboration between the North East & North Cumbria, North West and Yorkshire & Humber Secure Data Environments (hereafter, NW SDE, NENC SDE, and Y&H SDE), part of the NHS Secure Data Environment Network in England (hereafter, SDE Network), to assess the operational feasibility of federation utilising three TREvolution capabilities.

Over the course of the project, PANORAMA partners undertook a programme of technical development, governance analysis, and practical testing across both the individual TREs as well as in the context of the federation. This included mapping existing TRE capabilities against the SATRE specification, assessing the functionality of 5STES to execute federated analytical workflows, and testing SACRO's effectiveness as a support tool in the disclosure control process. Alongside this technical work, the project generated guidance, evaluation reports, and principles intended to support future TREvolution capability adopters. The project produced a range of publicly available outputs [2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10] that demonstrate both what is currently possible and what further work is needed to support wider adoption.

PANORAMA provides practical evidence that secure, federated research across multiple TREs is achievable, but cannot just be limited to technical tools. PANORAMA demonstrates that technical tools support federation, but trust, governance equivalence, and inter-organisational operational alignment determine whether it succeeds. By identifying both benefits and limitations, PANORAMA supports national efforts to improve federated sensitive data research infrastructure and accelerates high-quality research that deliver public benefit in a trustworthy and transparent way.

1.2. Overview of TREvolution Capabilities Utilised

1.2.1. SATRE

The SATRE (Standard Architecture for Trusted Research Environments) capability was used within PANORAMA as a structured framework for assessing whether TRE infrastructure, data management and information governance can be considered equivalent, and whether equivalence can enable a federated Information Governance (IG) framework at an organisational level. SATRE provides a common reference model for describing TRE components, controls, and capabilities across technical, governance and operational domains. Within PANORAMA, SATRE was applied throughout the project to support self-assessment, cross-functional dialogue, and comparative analysis across organisations. SATRE was not used as a compliance checklist; rather, PANORAMA tested whether SATRE could be used as a tool to create organisation-level federation.

1.2.2. 5STES

The 5 Safes Trusted Execution Service (5STES) capability was used within PANORAMA to explore the feasibility of federated analytics [11] across multiple Trusted Research Environments. 5STES is designed to distribute analytical code written by researchers within a federation; TRE staff execute the code locally and return the aggregated results back to the researcher. This enables results to be combined across federations without centralising sensitive row-level data. Within the project, technical teams across PANORAMA undertook feasibility assessments of installation, use and maintenance of the tool within a federation. The feasibility assessment of 5STES allowed PANORAMA to move beyond theoretical discussions of federated analytics and to evaluate practical considerations such as workflow coordination, technical governance and the operational realities of maintaining software both locally and across a federation. The 5STES capability was treated as an exploratory and developmental tool rather than a production service given the tool's development stage during PANORAMA's testing, with emphasis placed on identifying dependencies, limitations and conditions required for sustainable federated analytics as a viable research methodology.

1.2.3. SACRO

The SACRO (Semi-Automated Checking of Research Outputs) capability was used within PANORAMA to evaluate the role of (semi-) automation in supporting output checking within and across TREs. Output checking is manual and time-consuming; SACRO aims to augment human review by applying automated rules and checks to research outputs, improving consistency and efficiency while maintaining appropriate oversight. Within the project, SACRO was explored during the later stages through pilot testing and workflow analysis involving TRE operations staff. The focus was on understanding how automated checks could be integrated into existing output checking processes, how results should be interpreted and where human judgement remains essential. PANORAMA also examined the implications of SACRO in federated contexts, including questions of accountability and assurance when outputs are generated across organisational boundaries. The capability was treated as a developmental tool, with evaluation centred on transparency and operational fit. Insights from this work informed recommendations on process governance, tooling maturity and future development priorities.

2. Feedback on the Capabilities Adopted

2.1. Utility of the Capabilities

2.1.1. SATRE

Work Package 1 of the PANORAMA project evaluated whether the Standard Architecture for Trusted Research Environments (SATRE) could be used to establish an organisation-level federated Information Governance (IG) framework across the NENC, NW and Y&H SDEs. Specifically, the work examined whether SATRE could support the assessment of *equivalence*, thereby enabling organisations to move beyond project-by-project governance towards a more streamlined, organisation-level federated model. Full findings are available in the [Work Package 1 Final Report](#).

SATRE was applied as a structured self-assessment framework across three NHS Secure Data Environments (SDEs), Individual SATRE assessments were collated into a comparative heatmap, allowing partners to visualise similarities and differences in governance and technical controls and TRE operational

processes. In practice, this comparative use of SATRE proved valuable. The heatmap enabled focused discussion on where organisations appeared aligned, where differences existed, and whether those differences were acceptable within a federated context. This moved discussions away from abstract notions of ‘trust’ towards concrete evidence and documented practices. SATRE’s breadth and neutrality (i.e., agnostic to organisational model and geography) made it suitable for this role and suggested its potential applicability beyond the PANORAMA context, including cross-national federation. However, the work also demonstrated that equivalence cannot be inferred from SATRE scores alone. Identical or similar scores did not necessarily imply that organisations interpreted criteria in the same way, implemented controls in comparable forms or would be comfortable relying on one another’s governance arrangements (and indeed, technical or operational arrangements) without further scrutiny.

A critical early finding was that federated IG work cannot proceed without a shared and explicitly agreed vocabulary. During initial workshops, it became evident that key terms such as *federation*, *information governance*, *framework*, *equivalence* and *tolerance* were being used differently by researchers and operational IG professionals, and sometimes differently between organisations. Before an equivalence exercise could meaningfully take place, PANORAMA therefore introduced a dedicated terminology workshop in which partners compared and reconciled definitions. Without a common language, discussions of equivalence risked becoming circular or misaligned, particularly where legal and governance professionals naturally defaulted to project-specific instruments such as Data Protection Impact Assessments (DPIAs), rather than organisation-level constructs. The work package demonstrates that **SATRE can help structure governance discussions, but it does not itself supply the shared semantic foundation required for federation.**

A second major insight was the importance of explicitly defining the scope of federation before undertaking equivalence assessment. Initially, PANORAMA assumed a general goal of organisation-level IG to support federated analytics. In practice, this proved insufficiently precise. IG professionals repeatedly contextualised governance in relation to specific data types, processing activities and risks, highlighting that equivalence judgments are inherently scope dependent. The methodology was therefore revised to clarify that the equivalence exercise concerned *organisation-level readiness for federation*, not approval of specific research projects and to narrow the equivalence focus to the SATRE Information Governance pillar. This reframing allowed participants to engage more productively, abstracting from immediate operational pressures while still grounding discussions in real evidence. The finding is clear: without agreed scope, equivalence assessment risks either over-generalisation or reversion to project-by-project governance.

The PANORAMA evaluation shows that **SATRE is effective as a foundational tool** for federated IG, but insufficient as a complete solution. Its strengths lie in:

- Providing comprehensive coverage of TRE governance requirements;
- Enabling structured comparison across organisations;
- Highlighting areas requiring negotiation, remediation, or explicit tolerance decisions; and
- Offering a repeatable baseline that can support ongoing assurance over time.

However, SATRE alone cannot establish a federated IG framework. It does not:

- Define acceptable tolerance thresholds between organisations;
- Resolve differences in legal interpretation or risk appetite;

- Specify the additional agreements, decision-making structures, or escalation routes required for federation; or
- Provide mechanisms for governing federation as a living, evolving arrangement.

Work Package 1 of PANORAMA therefore positions SATRE as an *enabler rather than a determinant* of federation. It supports the identification of equivalence and clarifies what additional governance processes are required, including mechanisms for monitoring equivalence over time to ensure sustainable federation. When combined with agreed vocabulary, clear scope, and sustained organisational commitment, SATRE can play a central role in building trust and transparency between federating TREs.

2.1.2. 5STES

Work Package 2 assessed the practical feasibility and utility of the 5 Safes Trusted Execution Service (5STES) as a capability to support federated analytics across multiple Trusted Research Environments (TREs). The evaluation was undertaken across PANORAMA partners operating heterogeneous cloud infrastructures, including Azure and Amazon Web Services (AWS). A key limitation of the findings is that the assessment took place while 5STES was still in an early development phase. Due to information security constraints associated with non-production-ready software, partners undertook test installations, architectural reviews, and limited functional testing rather than full deployment into live TRE environments. The primary objective was therefore exploratory: to determine whether, how, and under what conditions 5STES could realistically support federated analytics in operational settings. A detailed technical assessment is documented in the [Work Package 2 Final Report](#).

At a conceptual level, 5STES was viewed positively by all partners. Its core design to execute standardised analytical code locally within each TRE and returning only aggregated results is strongly aligned with the Five Safes principles and with established expectations around data minimisation and security. The separation of submission, execution and egress stages was recognised by platform and infrastructure specialists as a sound architectural foundation to enable federated analytics workflows, particularly in contexts where data controllers are unwilling or unable to permit centralised data pooling. This provided confidence that federated analytics without data movement is achievable in principle. In practice, however, PANORAMA feasibility testing (Sept-Nov 2025) revealed significant constraints on the immediate utility of 5STES. Only one of the three partner organisations was able to complete a test installation of 5STES, and this was limited to executing a basic 'Hello World' task. The remaining partners were unable to complete installations within the project timeframe due to a combination of security restrictions and the operational burden associated with the system's complexity. As a result, no end-to-end federated analytical workflow was executed across the PANORAMA federation.

The most significant technical limitation identified was architectural complexity. At the time of evaluation, 5STES required the deployment and maintenance of approximately 15–25 interconnected containers per TRE, alongside secure secrets management, authentication services, logging infrastructure, and internal network connectivity between components. Extending this architecture to operate across federated TREs would introduce additional, unquantified operational overhead. While technically robust and flexible, this architecture was consistently assessed by platform engineers and operations teams as exceeding the capacity of most TRE teams to support sustainably, particularly when multiplied across organisations.

The feasibility assessment also highlighted that the utility of 5STES is tightly coupled to broader ecosystem readiness rather than the tool alone. For example, 5STES assumes that data are mapped to a common data

model (e.g., OMOP) and that this mapping must be sufficiently consistent across organisations to support shared analytical code. This consistency must be achieved at both breadth of data (e.g., equivalent databases/datasets across organisations) as well as depth (e.g., mappings consistently applied to individual variables). Whilst PANORAMA partners have an agreed variable mapping, this only consists of 42 variables to support cohort discovery, and no dataset/database prioritisation order. Considering that many of the datasets/databases consists of hundreds or thousands of variables, this is insufficient to support 'federated analysis' in its broadest sense. Federated analytics using 5STES in practice requires significant upfront investment in data standardisation, independent of the tool itself.

Governance and operational considerations further constrained utility. Although 5STES includes a manual egress approval step aligned with the Safe Outputs principle, PANORAMA identified that federated analytics would significantly increase the volume and coordination complexity of output checking. Without agreed inter-organisational operating procedures, service level agreements, and clear accountability models, federated egress was viewed as operationally unsustainable. These challenges were not attributed to deficiencies in 5STES but rather highlighted the necessity of mature operational governance alongside technical capabilities.

Despite these constraints, **WP2 generated important qualitative insights into how 5STES could evolve into a viable capability.** The capability was not suitable for production use at the time of testing, but it proved highly valuable as a feasibility probe that surfaced the technical and organisational preconditions required for federated analytics at scale. **PANORAMA demonstrates that federated analytics execution is technically achievable, but also that success depends less on the availability of novel tooling and more on simplification, standardisation, and alignment with the operational realities of TREs.** These findings provide clear, evidence-based guidance for future development of 5STES and for organisations considering federated analytics as part of their research infrastructure.

2.1.3. SACRO

The SACRO capability explored within PANORAMA addressed one of the most operationally intensive and risk-sensitive aspects of TRE operation: the checking of research outputs to prevent disclosure of sensitive information. The aim of Work Package 3 was to assess whether SACRO could support existing manual output checking processes by improving efficiency and consistency, whilst maintaining appropriate human oversight and accountability. WP3 also sought to understand the requirements to successfully undertake statistical disclosure control within federated operational processes. Comprehensive testing and discussion are available in the [Work Package 3 Final Report](#).

Within PANORAMA, SACRO tools were evaluated through a series of pilot activities that focused on common output types, particularly tabular summaries and descriptive statistics. These pilots provided concrete evidence that automated rules and statistical checks can reliably identify a range of well-understood disclosure risks, including small cell counts, dominance and certain forms of differencing. In doing so, SACRO could reduce the manual effort required for routine checks and improve consistency across decisions for *routine, low risk* checks. However, rather than being deployed as a fully automated solution, SACRO was deliberately assessed in PANORAMA only as a decision-support for human reviewers to assess. This positioning was central to its acceptability and perceived usefulness in practice.

Qualitative feedback from tests indicated that SACRO was most effective when integrated early in the output checking workflow. By flagging potential issues before formal review, the tool could enable

reviewers to focus attention on higher-risk elements rather than re-checking routine outputs. Although quantitative time savings were not formally measured during the pilot, staff observations consistently suggested that SACRO could reduce review effort and cognitive load if deployed at scale, but only when combined with clear standard operating procedures. From a governance perspective, SACRO was valued for its potential to improve transparency and auditability. The tool records which checks are applied and what flags are raised, creating an explicit evidence trail to support decision-making. Governance leads noted that this could strengthen internal assurance processes and support external scrutiny by making output checking decisions more defensible and reproducible.

The evaluation also surfaced important limitations. SACRO's utility declined for non-standard statistical outputs, where disclosure risk depends heavily on context, analytical intent and professional judgement. In such cases, automated checks were insufficient on their own and required careful human interpretation. This reinforced the conclusion that **SACRO cannot replace skilled output checkers but can support them by handling predictable and repeatable checks.**

At the same time, PANORAMA found that SACRO should not be treated as 'the solution' to manual output checking. SACRO requires careful configuration, validation and ongoing maintenance to remain effective. Changes in research practices, data types, or regulatory expectations can all affect the suitability of automated rules. Without appropriate resourcing and governance, there is a risk that automated checks could become outdated or misaligned with organisational risk appetite. **PANORAMA demonstrated that SACRO, has the potential to enhance existing processes but does not remove the need for skilled, human judgement or robust governance and processes.**

2.2. Impact of Using the TRevolution Capabilities

The combined testing of SATRE, 5STES and SACRO within PANORAMA had an impact on how partners understood their current operations and how these capabilities could support future development of their TREs. The strength in considering the TRevolution capabilities together and within a federation led to valuable insights, exposing structural dependencies between technology, governance and operational practice. Across PANORAMA, one of the most immediate impacts of testing the feasibility of the TRevolution capabilities was the socio-technical complexity of federation, and that the capabilities in and of themselves are not sufficient to create a 'secure, connected, and interoperable network of TREs for sensitive data research across the UK' [12]. However, the capabilities can be used to support this aim.

2.2.1. Contributions of the capabilities to PANORAMA organisations

SATRE played a central role in this by providing PANORAMA a clear reference architecture against which existing practices could be assessed. This enabled organisations to move away from informal or historically evolved processes toward more explicit and documented evidence against a clear specification. In the context of federated IG, the use of SATRE highlighted where governance processes were implicit or dependent on individual expertise. In response, organisations began to consider and address roles and responsibilities both within and across each federation partner that would support organisation-level federated IG. Whilst PANORAMA established that SATRE cannot establish a federated IG framework in and of itself, testing its utility in the context of a federation resulted in a structured methodology for other organisations to use when considering the adoption of an organisation-level IG framework, and provides the capability with useful insights that will help establish a federation pillar in future iterations of SATRE

PANORAMA's testing of 5STES to support federated analysis within a federation further stressed the importance of robust governance. Federated workflows required explicit agreement on approval processes, execution responsibilities, and escalation pathways across organisational boundaries. Similarly, the evaluation of SACRO considered the utility of semi-automated checks, enabling organisations to distinguish between routine checks that could be systematised and complex decisions that required expert judgement. Likewise, it prompted consideration of how output checking processes must necessarily change within the context of the federation.

As a DARE UK Early Adopter, PANORAMA's key learning was that successful federation requires significant organisational preparedness. While evaluations of SATRE, 5STES and SACRO showed that equivalence assessment, federated analytics and automation of output checking are technically feasible, their effectiveness is limited by the operational capacity, shared interpretations, agreed tolerances and governance needed to sustain them. Taken together, these findings reinforce that technology can enable federation, but it is the alignment of operational governance, organisational processes and inter-organisational trust that ultimately determines whether federation succeeds in practice.

2.2.2. Sector Benefits

Beyond individual organisations, PANORAMA demonstrated how TRevolution capabilities can contribute to broader sectoral benefits, generating evidence that can inform national policy and future infrastructure development.

PANORAMA reinforces the importance of shared standards and principles as enablers of collaboration and public trust. It also highlighted the risks of attempting early adoption of immature tools without adequate investment. These insights are directly relevant to the wider UK TRE Community and to programmes seeking to scale secure data research nationally. **The impacts observed in PANORAMA suggest that TRevolution capabilities have the potential to transform how sensitive data is used for federated research, but only if they are adopted as part of coherent cross-organisational change and grounded in operational reality rather than as isolated technical solutions.**

Among PANORAMA's outputs, three stand out for their direct operational impact on how organisations approach federation: (1) the development of a [practical, implementable methodology to support organisation-level federated IG](#); (2) the articulation of [federated output statistical disclosure control principles](#) designed to be applied within real-world TRE operations; and (3) [Federated Technical Development Principles](#). Taken together, these outputs have the potential to transform policy and sector practice by shifting the focus of federation away from purely technical integration towards the socio-technical foundations of trust, equivalence, accountability, governance and operational processes that ultimately determine whether federated systems function effectively in practice.

2.3. Public Involvement and Engagement (PIE)

2.3.1. Activities

PANORAMA was supported by a robust programme of Public Involvement and Engagement (PIE) designed to explore public understanding of, and views on, data federation within TREs. Federation is a relatively new and often abstract concept for the public, and the engagement therefore focused not only on whether federation was acceptable in principle, but on the conditions under which it would be considered trustworthy in practice. The work brought together insights from three complementary engagement

activities delivered across the North of England, enabling both regional comparison and identification of shared themes. Each activity was designed to explore public perceptions of the benefits and risks of federated data arrangements, alongside expectations around governance, accountability, transparency, and control. A shared set of prompts and themes was used across all three regions to support comparability, while allowing space for locally specific concerns and priorities to emerge.

Recruitment approaches were tailored to local contexts but grounded in best practice principles. The Yorkshire and Humber Citizens' Jury used a two-stage civic lottery approach to recruit 25 jurors reflecting a broad cross-section of the regional population across geography, age, gender, ethnicity and socio-economic status. In the North East and North Cumbria, public input was provided through a standing panel of volunteer public members embedded within the NENC SDE's formal governance and accountability structures. In the North West, engagement was delivered through existing patient and public advisory structures across Cheshire and Merseyside, Greater Manchester, Lancashire and South Cumbria, and the regional Patient Advisory and Accountability Group, with open recruitment processes supported by the Research for the Future campaign. [Work Package 4 Final Report](#) provides findings from across the North of England.

Across all three regions, participants were broadly supportive of the potential public benefits of federated data arrangements, particularly where federation could enable larger-scale research, support studies of rarer conditions, reduce duplication and improve understanding of health inequalities through comparison across populations. Participants also recognised potential efficiency gains for researchers through simplified access processes. However, this support was conditional rather than unconditional, and confidence consistently diminished as discussions moved from high-level principles to practical implementation.

Public concerns centred on governance and accountability, particularly whether local standards, oversight and public voice would be protected within a federated model. Participants raised questions about operational integrity, including data accuracy, consistency and the risk of errors across interconnected systems. Commercial access to data emerged as a significant trust issue, with concerns about transparency, fairness, pricing and assurance of public benefit. Fears of 'boundary creep' were also evident, reflecting anxieties that federation could enable future data uses beyond current public expectations within a particular region. Across all regions, lack of clarity about *what federation means in practice* was identified as a major source of uncertainty.

While these themes were consistent, regional variation was also apparent. Participants in the North East and North Cumbria placed particular emphasis on governance, local control, and the avoidance of 'jurisdiction shopping'. In the North West, concerns focused more strongly on practical delivery risks and system robustness. In Yorkshire and Humber, discussions highlighted fairness, transparency and the role of commercial organisations. Across all settings, inconsistent terminology and shifting narratives were found to undermine confidence, even amongst participants who were otherwise supportive of data use for research.

The PANORAMA public engagement work establishes a clear response agenda informed directly by public input that is equally applicable to the wider TRevolution programme. This includes the need for plain-language explanations of federation supported by clear visual materials; greater clarity around governance, accountability and the maintenance of local oversight; transparent principles for commercial involvement; harmonised or equivalent minimum standards alongside legitimate local variation; and stronger assurance

about how issues will be addressed and future changes managed. Further work is required to document how these recommendations are implemented and to evidence impact over time.

Several lessons emerge clearly from this work and aligns with findings from Work Package 1 and applicable to Work Packages 2 and 3. Trust must be actively designed and demonstrated. Clarity and consistency of communication are critical, as confusion about federation and unexplained shifts in language can quickly undermine confidence. Regional variation in concerns is meaningful and should inform engagement and assurance approaches. **Above all, governance questions—particularly around accountability, commercial use and responses to failure—dominate public discussion and must be addressed directly if federated data models are to maintain public trust. Federation is not rejected by the public, but it raises expectations around transparency, accountability and demonstrable safeguards that cannot be met through reassurance alone.**

2.3.2. Additional Findings: Designing a Federated Insights Dashboard

Working across DARE UK Early Adopters, PPIE experts from Lancashire Teaching Hospitals NHS Foundation Trust and [Focus-5 DARE UK Early Adopter project](#), previously led the development of a Patient and Public Involvement and Engagement (PPIE) insights dashboard to support PPIE practitioners in collating and analysing public involvement and engagement activities. An outcome of cross-working between the PANORAMA and Focus-5 DARE UK Early Adopters was a re-conceptualisation of the insights dashboard for use within federated data ecosystems. Rather than treating public engagement as a series of isolated, local activities, the work reframed PPIE insights as a shared, strategic asset capable of informing decision-making across organisational boundaries. The [federated insights dashboard](#) is intended to collate, structure and visualise insights from diverse engagement activities, enabling TREs operating within a federation to identify common themes, surface regional variation, and better understand the perspectives of different population groups, including historically underrepresented groups. By supporting comparative analysis and longitudinal tracking of public views, the dashboard offers a practical mechanism to enhance transparency, strengthen accountability, and support more responsive and inclusive engagement practices within a federated sensitive data research ecosystem. This initial conceptual work demonstrates how PPIE activities can be considered in federated contexts and designed and delivered coordinated, insight-led approach that deepens understanding of public expectations around sensitive data research.

2.4. Overall Drawbacks and Recommendations for Improvement

While the adoption of SATRE, 5STES, and SACRO within PANORAMA delivered clear benefits, the project also surfaced several limitations and challenges. These drawbacks are important to articulate explicitly, both to set realistic expectations for future adopters and to inform the further development of TRevolution capabilities. This section consolidates evidence presented above in sections 2.1, 2.2 and 2.3 to identify areas requiring improvement.

2.4.1. SATRE

While SATRE proved valuable as a structured framework for documenting and comparing organisational controls, PANORAMA identified clear limitations in its ability to directly establish a federated information governance (IG) framework. PANORAMA found that SATRE assumes a shared understanding of governance concepts and terminology that does not exist by default across organisations. Significant effort was required to align definitions and scope before equivalence assessment could meaningfully proceed.

These findings demonstrate that while SATRE is a valuable enabling tool for federated IG, it cannot deliver federation in isolation and must be complemented by agreed vocabularies, clearly defined scope and sustained inter-organisational governance processes. PANORAMA therefore suggests that future development of SATRE should be accompanied by stronger implementation support. This includes worked examples, maturity models, and guidance on how organisations at different stages of development can pragmatically engage with the specification. Without such support, the full potential of SATRE is unlikely to be realised.

2.4.2. 5STES

The 5STES capability exposed a different set of drawbacks, primarily related to complexity, readiness and scalability. While federated analysis was shown to be technically feasible, PANORAMA demonstrated that it is not a low-cost or low-effort alternative to traditional data sharing models. Instead, it shifts complexity from data movement to coordination, orchestration, and governance alignment. Installation, deployment and connectivity between TREs will require bespoke solutions and extensive manual coordination, limiting the scalability and repeatability of the approach. Federated workflows introduced new demands on staff time and expertise, particularly in areas such as job orchestration, monitoring, troubleshooting and inter-organisational communication. In the absence of dedicated resourcing, these demands risk becoming unsustainable. This finding reinforces the lesson that federation should be treated as a strategic capability requiring investment, rather than as an incremental extension of existing operations. Partners consistently observed that a simplified variant of 5STES—with fewer components, clearer deployment patterns and reduced operational overhead—would significantly improve adoptability. Comparative analysis with existing federated tools demonstrated that lower architectural complexity and production-readiness are critical determinants of uptake, particularly for organisations with limited DevOps capacity.

2.4.3. SACRO

SACRO is the more 'production-ready' tool for deployment in TREs, but for PANORAMA partners, still exhibited clear limitations. While semi-automated output checking was effective for routine outputs, PANORAMA confirmed that the approach does not generalise easily to more complex or novel output types. Visualisations, model parameters, and machine learning artefacts present disclosure risks that are difficult to capture through fixed rules or automated checks. Considering that output checking is a critical control point with legal, ethical and reputational implications, PANORAMA observed that introducing automation into this process requires careful change management. Reviewers must understand how automated checks operate, what their limitations are and when human judgement must override automated outputs. Without this understanding, there is a risk of over-confidence in automation.

The federated dimension introduced additional complexity. PANORAMA found that without shared principles for federated output checking, automated tools risk being applied inconsistently across organisations, undermining trust in combined outputs. The development of Federated OSDC Principles was therefore a necessary complement to the tooling, but these principles themselves require further operationalisation. Overall, PANORAMA suggests that SACRO should be positioned as an enabling component within a broader output checking ecosystem, rather than as a standalone solution. Further development is required to expand coverage, improve transparency and support integration into diverse operational contexts.

3. Feedback on the Adoption Process

3.1. Challenges Encountered and Identification Process

The feasibility testing of SATRE, 5STES, and SACRO within PANORAMA revealed a range of technical, organisational and practical challenges. These challenges did not emerge uniformly or at a single point in the project; rather, they became visible progressively as the project moved from design to practical feasibility testing. Importantly, many challenges were not initially anticipated and only became apparent through hands-on engagement with the capabilities in operational contexts.

A recurring theme across all three capabilities was the gap between conceptual readiness and operational readiness. Early in the project, during planning and design stages, the capabilities were largely perceived as well aligned with organisational aspirations since they were tools developed as part of DARE UK Phase 1. It was only when teams attempted to apply them to real systems, workflows and governance processes that constraints and friction became visible.

Across all three capabilities, a common challenge was resourcing and capacity. Adoption activities required sustained engagement from staff with specialised expertise, often alongside existing operational responsibilities. This challenge was identified by project leads and managers throughout the project and was only partially mitigated through prioritisation and scope management. It reinforced the insight that adoption of complex capabilities requires dedicated investment rather than being absorbed into business-as-usual activity.

Challenges within PANORAMA became visible primarily through practical engagement rather than abstract planning. They were identified by technical staff, governance leads, operational teams and project managers at different stages of the project lifecycle. While some challenges were resolved through adaptation and collaboration, others highlighted structural constraints that extend beyond the scope of PANORAMA. These findings provide a realistic account of the effort required to adopt emerging TRevolution capabilities and set an important context for the recommendations that follow.

3.2. Recommendations for Improving the Adoption Process

The experience of adopting SATRE, 5STES and SACRO within PANORAMA highlights several ways in which the adoption process could be improved for future adopters. These recommendations are framed explicitly from the perspective of organisations attempting to integrate emerging TRevolution capabilities into existing technical, governance and operational environments.

3.2.1. Changes to Onboarding, Training, or Documentation

A consistent and critical lesson from PANORAMA is that early adopters require significantly more structured onboarding than is currently available. While the conceptual intent of SATRE, 5STES, and SACRO was generally understood by participating organisations, substantial effort was required to translate high-level descriptions into operational understanding. This gap was most acute in operational settings, where staff are required to make day-to-day decisions about deployment, governance, and service delivery. Without onboarding that is explicitly designed to support operational implementation, wider adoption of these capabilities in live TRE environments will not occur. Effective onboarding must therefore be recognised as a prerequisite for operational uptake, not an optional enhancement.

Training must also move beyond descriptive overviews of capability intent and architecture. PANORAMA demonstrates that future adoption will depend on training that is tailored to distinct audiences, including technical implementers, information governance leads and TRE operations staff. Training should incorporate scenario-based examples grounded in real TRE workflows, such as federated governance decision-making, execution of federated analyses, and coordinated output checking across organisations. These applied scenarios are essential to enable staff to understand how capabilities function in practice, how responsibilities are distributed, and how risks are managed in operational contexts.

In parallel, documentation requires a fundamental shift in focus towards implementation within federated settings. Existing documentation largely describes how capabilities function within single organisations, offering limited guidance on how they should be deployed, governed and sustained across organisational boundaries. PANORAMA highlights that federation introduces additional layers of complexity, including shared accountability, inter-organisational assurance, and operational coordination, which must be explicitly addressed in implementation guidance. Comprehensive, federation-aware documentation is therefore a foundational requirement for enabling a scalable federated TRE ecosystem.

These changes could be addressed by sustained investment rather than ad hoc support to move beyond research or pilot settings. A practical mechanism to support these recommendations would be for DARE UK to commit dedicated funding to the development and maintenance of structured onboarding, role-specific training and implementation-focused documentation for current and future federation capabilities.

3.2.2. Suggested Technical Improvements or Additional Support

From a technical perspective, PANORAMA indicates that future adopters would benefit from greater availability of reference implementations, integration patterns, and tooling support. While flexibility is an important design principle, the absence of concrete examples increases the burden on adopters and leads to duplication of effort. For SATRE, this will be reviewing the existing criteria, providing clearer guidance and terminology and introducing a federation pillar. For federated analysis, additional support is needed around orchestration, monitoring, and error handling particularly in heterogeneous environments. Without such support, the technical complexity of federation risks becoming a barrier to adoption. For SACRO, technical improvements should focus on expanding coverage to a wider range of output types and improving transparency of automated checks. Adopters will also require guidance on how to validate and maintain automated rules over time. Across all capabilities, access to responsive technical support during adoption phases would significantly reduce friction and build confidence.

3.2.3. Adjustments to Communication, Sequencing, or Workflows

PANORAMA demonstrated that the sequencing of adoption activities has a substantial impact on success. Future adopters would benefit from clearer guidance on the order in which capabilities should be explored and integrated. For example, using SATRE to establish a shared understanding of TRE capability and readiness before attempting federated analysis or automated output checking may remove barriers to technologies caused by lack of operational equivalence and alignment of federating TREs.

Communication practices also require attention. Adoption efforts were most effective when there were regular, structured opportunities for cross-functional and cross-organisational dialogue. Future adoption programmes must explicitly build in mechanisms for sharing assumptions, surfacing concerns and reflecting on progress, rather than relying on informal or ad hoc communication. This must be between capability development teams as well as between federation partners.

Workflow adjustments are particularly important where new capabilities intersect with established practices. SACRO adoption, for example, was more successful where output checking workflows were explicitly redesigned to incorporate automated checks, rather than attempting to insert tools into existing processes without modification. Similar considerations apply to federated analysis workflows, which require clear handoffs and responsibilities across organisational boundaries.

3.2.4. Organisational or Structural Recommendations

At an organisational level, PANORAMA underscores the importance of treating federation and associated capabilities as a strategic activity rather than as an add-on to business-as-usual operations. Future adopters should ensure that adoption efforts are supported by clear leadership, defined ownership and dedicated resourcing. Without this structural support, even well-designed capabilities risk stalling at the pilot stage.

Structural alignment between technical, governance and operational functions is also critical. Adoption was most effective where organisations created spaces for these groups to work together, rather than progressing in parallel. This is particularly important for federated capabilities, which cut across traditional organisational boundaries and challenge existing lines of accountability.

Finally, funders and programme designers should recognise that early adoption of complex socio-technical capabilities requires sustained investment. PANORAMA demonstrated that meaningful adoption cannot be achieved through short-term pilots alone. Long-term commitment to capability development, organisational learning and practitioner community building are essential if TRevolution capabilities are to transition from experimental tools to reliable components of national sensitive data research infrastructure.

3.3. Lessons Learnt

The PANORAMA project provides a clear and evidence-based account of what it means to act as an early adopter of complex, emerging socio-technical capabilities within the TRE ecosystem. While the project demonstrated the value and potential of the TRevolution programme, it also surfaced important lessons about the limits of early adoption.

3.3.1. What Could Have Been Done Differently

In retrospect, PANORAMA would have benefited from a clearer distinction, from the outset, between exploratory evaluation and operational adoption. Although the project was framed as an Early Adopter initiative, the TRevolution capabilities are still at an early stage of development. This created tension between the aspiration to integrate tools into operational workflows and the reality that some components were not yet sufficiently mature, documented or supported for sustained use. Whilst some were suitable for testing in individual environments, none were suitable within a federation.

PANORAMA also underestimated the level of inter- and cross-organisational change required to support federation. While technical feasibility was less of a barrier, the governance, legal and operational implications of federation cannot be understated. Whilst deeper engagement earlier on with socio-technical dimensions would have strengthened planning, there must be a concerted effort at a national level via organisations and policy-makers to provide increased guidance to reduce variability in interpretation and decision-making to aid the process of implementing and operationalising federation capabilities. This is particularly critical to supporting information governance, where differing risk appetites towards sensitive data research poses a significant barrier to federated research.

3.3.2. What Went Well and Should Be Repeated

Despite these challenges, several aspects of PANORAMA worked well and should be actively repeated in future programmes. Chief among these was the decision to engage deeply and critically with capabilities rather than treating adoption as a box-ticking exercise. The project created space for honest assessment, including acknowledgement of limitations and unresolved issues, which significantly enhanced the credibility of its findings.

The use of SATRE as a shared reference framework was particularly effective. It enabled structured dialogue across technical, governance and operational domains and provided a stable anchor for discussions about maturity and readiness. This approach should be considered a core component of future TRevolution adoption efforts.

Hands-on engagement with the technical tools was another strength. The 5STES and SACRO evaluations generated insights that could not have been obtained through documentation review alone. This experiential learning was invaluable for PANORAMA partners and underscores the importance of supporting practical experimentation within real-world environments.

3.3.3. Unexpected Findings or Insights

One of the most significant unexpected insights from PANORAMA was the extent to which products developed within research programmes require transformation before they can be used operationally. While this is not unique to TRevolution capabilities, the project highlighted how easily this gap can be underestimated. Research-grade tools often lack the robustness, usability, and support structures required for operational environments, particularly those dealing with sensitive data.

Another important insight concerned federation. PANORAMA demonstrated that federation is not simply a technical architecture but a fundamental shift in how responsibility, trust and accountability are distributed. Attempting to retrofit federated use into tools or governance frameworks designed for single organisations proved consistently challenging. This reinforces the need for federation-by-design, rather than federation-by-extension.

The project also revealed that transparency is a critical enabler of trust. Whether in architectural assessment, federated execution, or output checking, the ability to explain how decisions are made and controls are applied was as important as the controls themselves. This has implications not only for technical design but for public and stakeholder confidence in TREs more broadly.

3.3.4. Advice for Future Adopters and for TRevolution and DARE UK

For future adopters, PANORAMA offers a clear conclusion: early adoption of complex capabilities should be approached as a learning exercise, not as a shortcut to operational transformation. Organisations should be realistic about the investment required, including time, expertise and organisational change. Adopters should prioritise understanding capability boundaries and dependencies before attempting integration into business-as-usual operations.

Future adopters should also resist the temptation to treat emerging tools as finished products. Active engagement, feedback, and iterative refinement are essential, but these activities require dedicated resourcing and should be recognised as such. Where possible, adoption efforts should focus on incremental integration, supported by clear success criteria and exit points.

For DARE UK, PANORAMA underscores the value of the TRevolution programme while also highlighting areas for refinement. **The findings from PANORAMA indicate that for TRevolution capabilities to be adopted at scale, DARE UK must complement technical development with a dedicated focus on socio-technical and operational implementation.** While existing efforts have successfully advanced tooling, the primary barriers to adoption lie in governance alignment, operational readiness and the translation of capabilities into day-to-day TRE practice. Without structured support for organisational change, capability onboarding and federated operational models, technically sound tools risk remaining confined to pilot or research settings.

A socio-technical workstream within TRevolution would address these gaps directly by developing shared operational frameworks, implementation guidance and training tailored to different organisational roles. This would support TREs in moving beyond conceptual alignment towards consistent and sustainable implementation. Crucially, this would expand the TRevolution programme to formally recognise that federation is not achieved through technology alone, but through the coordinated design of tools, processes and inter-organisational trust. Embedding socio-technical and operational considerations within TRevolution is therefore essential to realising its ambition of a scalable, trusted federated UK data ecosystem.

4. Conclusions and Future Direction

4.1. Conclusions

The PANORAMA project has provided a rigorous and evidence-based assessment of the opportunities and challenges associated with early adoption of TRevolution capabilities within operational TREs. By engaging deeply with SATRE, federated analysis through 5STES, and SACRO, the project moved beyond conceptual endorsement and tested the feasibility of implementing these capabilities in real organisational contexts.

A central conclusion is that TRevolution capabilities address genuine and pressing needs within the TRE ecosystem to enable federation. At the same time, PANORAMA demonstrated that these capabilities cannot be adopted successfully without significant organisational engagement, sustained investment and realistic expectations about maturity and readiness. The project's findings underscore that innovation in TREs is not constrained primarily by technology, but by the socio-technical systems within which technology must operate.

4.2. Future Use of TRevolution Capabilities

The future use of TRevolution capabilities informed by PANORAMA's findings must be planned and context aware. While the project has demonstrated the value of SATRE, 5STES, and SACRO, it has also shown that not all capabilities are ready for immediate scaling or embedding into business-as-usual operations.

SATRE is well positioned for wider adoption and could be scaled across organisations as a foundational capability. Its use as a diagnostic and planning tool aligns well with ongoing efforts to professionalise and standardise TRE operations. Embedding SATRE into routine architectural review, assurance processes, and organisational development programmes would provide sustained benefit and support long-term capability improvement. Federated analysis, as explored through 5STES, requires a more cautious approach. While

additional pilots are both necessary and desirable, widespread rollout is contingent on further development of supporting infrastructure, governance models and operational practices. Future pilots should focus on clearly defined use cases where federation offers demonstrable advantage, and where participating organisations are prepared to invest in the required coordination not only on federated analytics, but the breadth and depth of common data models. SACRO occupies an intermediate position. Elements of automated output checking can be embedded incrementally into existing workflows, particularly where they support consistency and reduce manual burden. However, full operationalisation will require further development, validation and consensus around governance and accountability and will only support human judgement rather than replace it. Federated output statistical disclosure control, either with or without the use of SACRO will require significant workflow development.

Across all capabilities, PANORAMA indicates that embedding federation into broader organisational strategies, funding programmes, and national initiatives will be essential to achieving operational success and sustainable impact.

4.3. Support Needed for Continued or Expanded Use

The PANORAMA project makes clear that continued or expanded use of TRevolution capabilities will require sustained and coordinated support. Technical capability alone is insufficient; adoption depends on a broader ecosystem of expertise, resources and shared understanding.

Technical support remains a priority, particularly for complex capabilities such as federated analysis and automated output checking. Future adopters will require access to reference implementations, integration guidance, and responsive support during early deployment phases. Without this, the technical burden placed on individual organisations risks slowing progress and increasing fragmentation. Training and capacity building are equally important. PANORAMA demonstrated that effective adoption depends on developing skills across technical, governance, and operational domains. Investment in training programmes, communities of practice, and cross-organisational knowledge exchange would significantly enhance readiness and reduce duplication of effort.

Funding and staffing support must also be recognised as essential. Early adoption places additional demands on organisations, particularly those already operating at capacity. Dedicated funding for adoption activities, including time for experimentation, evaluation, and iteration, will be critical if TRevolution capabilities are to move beyond pilot projects.

Finally, further documentation and knowledge sharing are needed to consolidate learning from early adopters. PANORAMA's experience highlights the value of transparent reporting, shared principles and openly available guidance. DARE UK is well positioned to curate and disseminate this knowledge, supporting a virtuous cycle of learning and improvement across the UK TRE ecosystem. Introducing additional funding support and expertise to address socio-technical considerations is critical for the success of TRevolution in real-world environments.

PANORAMA affirms both the ambition and the necessity of the TRevolution programme. The project demonstrates that meaningful progress to federation is achievable, but only through sustained investment in people, processes and partnerships alongside technology enhancements. By acting on PANORAMA's findings, DARE UK can ensure that TRevolution capabilities mature into trusted, scalable components of the UK's sensitive data research infrastructure.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare.

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